

DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *The article provides a statistical analysis of small business and private entrepreneurship, economic development and legal framework, taxation on income and single tax payment. Creation of new jobs to ensure a stable and flexible development of small business in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the conditions of market conditions.*

Keywords: *small business and private entrepreneurship, gross domestic product, credit, taxes, exports, imports, services, agriculture, industry.*

The potential and role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economy of Uzbekistan is very important. They have an advantage over large enterprises in creating new jobs. This is because gross jobs created by small businesses are a companion to cheaper capital capacity than those created in large enterprises. It takes a short time to create them. Small business serves to increase the competitiveness of goods produced in the country in foreign markets. Expands exports, increases the

demand for them in the domestic market by improving the quality of goods.

Creating the necessary conditions for the sustainable development of small business and private entrepreneurship is an important condition for the formation of effective market relations in society, support for the property class and the establishment of new democratic institutions of civil society. This is an important task and the whole complexity of its solution, due to the

specificity of each country, requires an unconventional, non-standard approach to the support and development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Small business and private entrepreneurship are an important type of economic activity aimed at more efficient use of resources for profit. This process is explained by:

1. Small business and private entrepreneurship means entrepreneurial activity of people related to risk liability;

2. Small business and private entrepreneurship will focus on more rational use of resources, which requires a limited and innovative approach;

3. Small business and private entrepreneurship are considered justified only if they bring additional income and profit.

It should be noted that Uzbekistan has created a stable legal framework that strengthens the priority of private property, which is the basis of a market economy. A favorable business environment and reliable legal guarantees have been created for the

formation of the middle class, the sustainable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is an important factor in increasing incomes. As a result, over the past decade, the share of small business in GDP increased from 31.1% to 52.5%, the employment rate in this sector increased from 49.7% to 74.5% of the total population employed in the economy. More than 47% of the population's income comes from entrepreneurial income.

One of the most important directions of economic reforms in Uzbekistan is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. Special attention is paid to the development of small business in our country, taking into account the opportunities to solve the problem of employment, ensure the abundance of the market and increase the competitiveness of the economy.

Like all other sectors, it is necessary to carry out socio-economic reforms, ensure economic growth,

modernize the industry, launch new production facilities, implement targeted programs, develop agriculture, support small business and private entrepreneurship. was performed. In particular, a system of wide-ranging benefits and preferences for financial support of business initiatives has been created through the gradual improvement of the regulatory framework for economic reforms. Private property rights and its protection have been strengthened. In recent years, more than fifteen laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the new edition "On protection of private property and guarantees of property rights", "On licensing procedures in the field of entrepreneurship", "On family business", "On guarantees of freedom of entrepreneurial activity" gi and other laws were passed. The activities of information and consultation centers, real estate agencies, enterprises assisting entrepreneurs in maintaining accounting documents have been improved in cities and districts. Law firms, brokerage houses, branches of commercial banks and

branches of insurance companies began to develop, providing fast, convenient and reliable customer service. In addition, 167 permitting procedures, 19 types of licensed activities, as well as 65 types of statistics and 6 types of tax reporting have been abolished in the last 4 years, and the amount of fees for issuing permits has been halved. The system of taxation of entrepreneurs, accounting and statistical reporting has been simplified. Conditions and opportunities have been created to increase the volume of exports of entrepreneurs' products. The scope of financial support for small business and private entrepreneurship is also expanding through the provision of soft and microcredits and the allocation of funds for the formation of start-up capital. Tax incentives were applied. The system of vocational education, information and communication system for small business and private entrepreneurship has been developed.

In recent years, the legal framework for supporting small business and private entrepreneurship

has been radically updated. The role of the courts in the protection of business entities has been increased, and some of the powers exercised by regulatory authorities for private business entities have been transferred to the courts. Registration and licensing have been simplified.

The norms of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also strengthen the regulation and guarantee of relations related to small business and private entrepreneurship. In particular, Article 164 of the Code stipulates that a property right is a person's right to own, use and dispose of his property voluntarily and for his own benefit, as well as to demand the elimination of any violation of his property rights by anyone. recorded. In general, the norms of the Civil Code regulate property and personal nonproperty relations of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Stimulation of the small business and private entrepreneurship sector in our country is one of the key strategic factors of socio-economic development of the republic. In the context of economic reforms in

Uzbekistan, the main stages of supporting private entrepreneurship are in line with the stages of economic reform. As support for private entrepreneurship is an integral part of a market economy, a link that ensures its smooth functioning, it does not lose its relevance at every stage of the sector's reforms, even when market relations are fully operational.

In the wider involvement of small business and private entrepreneurship, special attention should be paid to the following issues:

- Expanding the access of small business and private entrepreneurship to loans, raw materials, as well as public procurement;
- Creation of organizational, legal, financial mechanisms and conditions necessary and favorable for the development of export potential of small business and private entrepreneurship;
- Establishment of systematic control over the allocation of targeted loans by government and nongovernmental organizations for small business and private

entrepreneurship to start their own business and ensure their spending;

- Further improvement of the necessary legal and regulatory documents aimed at the formation and strengthening of the middle class through the further development of small business and private entrepreneurship among young people on the basis of modern requirements;

- It is necessary to increase the number of small enterprises processing agricultural products in the country;

- It is necessary to further increase the number of small enterprises processing secondary waste, producing industrial products;

- It is necessary to further increase the number of small enterprises

engaged in the introduction of information and communication technologies in production.

Conclusion

From the above, it can be concluded that if the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is given priority, the country will develop socio-economically. This, in turn, will provide a solution to the problem of creating new jobs and thus the formation of effective intersectoral employment, increase incomes and strengthen mutually beneficial relations between different sectors.

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